

OVERVIEW OF GROUNDWATER RESOURCES IN BULGARIA

ПРЕГЛЕД РЕСУРСА ПОДЗЕМНИХ ВОДА У БУГАРСКОЈ

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ABSTRACT: *Groundwater serves as the primary water supply source for settlements across Bulgaria, offering significant reserves despite challenges in extraction. The systematic study of groundwater in Bulgaria commenced in the early 20th century, evolving from early measurements of spring flow rates to modern hydrogeological surveys covering a substantial portion of the country's territory. There are few stages of groundwater resource assessment which are pointing to the nowadays european approaches. Notable contributions include the delineation of aquifers, assessment of mineral waters, and mapping of groundwater resources across various geological settings. Methodologies for assessing groundwater resources in Bulgaria encompass specialized hydrogeological mapping, resource estimation, and basin management planning. Challenges such as climate change impacts and regulatory compliance with EU directives are addressed, emphasizing the need for ongoing monitoring and modern technologies like modeling of groundwater bodies.*

Key words: *groundwater resources, hydrogeology, Bulgaria*

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is the main source of water supply for settlements in Bulgaria. They form significant resources and reserves of water, despite their slow circulation and difficulties in their extraction. The constant connection of groundwater with rivers and surface water bodies contributes to balancing the water regime of different origins and ensures water supply even in remote areas.

Since underground waters are formed in different conditions, there is a certain specificity in the study and systematization of their resources related to the knowledge of the geological environment and the conditions of recharge and drainage of the aquifers. It is necessary to determine and control groundwater resources with a view to preserving their quantitative status and proper functioning of water extraction facilities.

STUDY OF GROUNDWATER IN BULGARIA

The systematic study of groundwater began at the beginning of the last century with the measurement of the flow rates of springs (Antonov et al., 1980). The first published data are related to the mineral waters in the town of Merichleri, and later on those in the towns of Varshets and Sliven. Gradually, after 1905, the mapping of shallow groundwater in arid regions such as Dobrudja began by French scientists, at the invitation of the Bulgarian government at the time. Prof. De Lone, together with L. Vankov and T. Mihailovski, compiled a map with hydroisohypses according to measured levels in boreholes and elevations of springs. The water supply of the town of Shumen is related to the study of the water-bearing capacity of the rocks of the Shumen plateau. In addition to water supply, the assessment of groundwater inflow is also related to mining activities. In 1939, R. Beregov published results on the behavior of confined aquifers in the Pliocene of the Lom depression, which flooded the coal and were an obstacle to its exploitation. The assessment carried out establishes the relationship between the groundwater levels and those of the Danube River.

As the beginning of the modern stage in Bulgarian hydrogeology can be considered the results of oil explorations in the area of the city of Varna, published in 1940-1941 by V. Tsankov, R. Beregov and El Cohen. The location was determined and a description of the aquifers was carried out, separating intervals with different mineralization. After 1948, the "Hydrogeological and Engineering Geological Surveys" Directorate of "Energoproject" conducted hydrogeological surveys to determine the fresh groundwater resources in the Dimitrovgrad region, the Upper Thracian Plain, the Kazanlak and Sofia Basins, the Danube Plains for the purpose of drinking, domestic and industrial water supply, as well as for irrigation. Until 1980, hydrogeological studies were carried out in 1/3 of the territory of Bulgaria, covering the most water-rich basins - lowlands, kettles, artesian basins, karst areas. Works related to the hydrogeological zoning of Bulgaria, karst groundwater and mineral waters Bulgaria have been completed. By 2000, significant factual material was accumulated, providing a basis for regional studies and guidelines for subsequent hydrogeological studies.

The improvement of theoretical training and the accumulation of sufficient volume of data on groundwater in Bulgaria contribute to the growth of proven specialists and scientists in the field of hydrogeology. Names such as N. Boyadzhiev, D. Yaranov, L. Berov, P. St. Petrov, D. Mollov, M. Galabov, Hr. Antonov, D. Danchev, P. Betsinski, K. Shterev, K. Petrov, Iv. Stanev, P. G. Petrov, V. Spasov, I. Yotov, E. Pencheva, I. Stefanov, Y. Straka, Bl. Raikova, Evg. Stoeva, Y. Ganchev, L. Vasileva, K. Boteva, T. Kehaiov and others. Regional hydrogeology also aims to determine the balance and resources of groundwater, as well as being related to their dynamics.

ASSESSMENT OF GROUNDWATER RESOURCES IN BULGARIA

Assessments of groundwater resources in Bulgaria have been made for different purposes, using different methods. The more significant of them can be grouped into the following categories:

- Resource assessments of groundwater for preparation of specialized hydrogeological maps: Map of natural and fresh groundwater, Map of forecast-exploitation resources of fresh groundwater, Map of the underground drainage of Eastern Europe 1:1500000.

The first major summary of groundwater resources is by preparation of the M 1:200000 Fresh Groundwater Natural and Projected Resource Maps (Bindemann et al., 1975, 1979), by a large group of hydrogeologists. According to the obtained results, the natural resources of groundwater were then 175 m³/s. About 42% (74 m³/s) of this amount of water falls on karst groundwater, both flowing from karst springs and forming the outflow of artesian karst aquifers (Upper Jurassic-Lower Cretaceous, Barremian-Aptian, Sarmatian). The exploitable resources of karst waters are estimated at about 42 m³/s (about 32% of the natural resources). Second in quantity are the waters formed in the alluvial deposits of the rivers and the Danube lowlands. Their natural resources amount to 52 m³/s (about 30% of their total amount). The evaluation of their exploitation possibilities includes additional resources of water from the rivers, the so-called "pull out" resources. The total value of these water resources is high, as from the Danube River alone, you can count on pilling out about 70 m³/s. The remaining approximately 40 m³/s of fresh groundwater resources are formed in other parts of the country, which are characterized by diverse hydrogeological conditions and a wide distribution of fracture waters. Groundwater formed in Quaternary, Pliocene and Paleogene deposits, filling tectonic depressions in southern Bulgaria are practically important. For example, only in the Upper Thracian Depression, the natural resources of groundwater amount to about 14 m³/s, most of which are exploited.

- A methodological guide developed by Prof. M. Galabov with co-authors (1999) presents the theoretical foundations for determining groundwater resources and gives as an example estimates for a number of real sites from Bulgaria.

- Groundwater resource assessments in the summary "General schemes for water use in River Basin management areas" (2000).

This assessment of groundwater uses information from existing maps of natural and estimated-exploitation resources in M 1:200000, revised and supplemented with data from more recent studies. Assessments of groundwater resources in the main catchment basins in the country are presented, with more serious attention being paid to the possibilities for their use. The results were summarized and published by Spasov et al. in 2003. Estimated operational resources for the country were set at 94 m³/s, and they are distributed unevenly in the four main areas with Basin Management (Fig. 1). As additional resources, the Danube and other rivers pull outs can be exploited up to 65 m³/s.

Figure 1. Distribution of exploitation resources from groundwater in the areas with River Basin management (according to Spasov et al., 2003)

- Groundwater resources in Bulgaria after the transition to the basin principle of water management

After the transition to the basin principle of water management in Bulgaria, continuous assessment and updating of the natural and available groundwater resources for each groundwater body is carried out. According to the Second River Basin Management Plans (2016-2021), published on the sites of the basin directorates, natural groundwater resources amount to 193 m³/s. They are unevenly distributed on the territory of the country (Fig. 2). The largest amount of groundwater is formed in the Danube Basin Management Region, which is due to both its largest area and the distribution of significant artesian aquifers on its territory. The water-rich Quaternary deposits in the Danube lowlands and river terraces are a good collector for groundwater. The lowest values of natural resources are determined in the West Belomorsi region, which also has the smallest area.

Figure 2. Distribution of natural groundwater resources in the Basin Management Areas according to the Second River Basin Management Plans (2016-2021)

According to the analyzes, about 6% (12.2 m³/s) of natural resources from groundwater are needed for the ecosystems that depend on them. Therefore, 181 m³/s of groundwater remains free for use.

Groundwater is an important source for providing water to the population, industry and agriculture. Their main advantages compared to surface waters are their significantly better protection from natural anthropogenic impacts, relatively more constant quantitative and physico-chemical indicators. The main features of their operation are related to the construction of additional groundwater facilities – boreholes and well, which are equipped in a suitable way.

According to data from the National Statistical Institute for the period 2003-2013, about 10% of the water used in Bulgaria is groundwater. The amount of groundwater used in the period 2018-2022 is between 514 and 566.10⁶ m³. The total amount used is related to water supply needs, agriculture (forestry, fisheries), industry, heat energy and other services. Traditionally, the largest percentage of groundwater falls on public water supply (water supply) and industry (in the processing industry).

The role of groundwater in North-Eastern Bulgaria and Dobrudja is most significant. Exploitation is carried out by drains, wells and boreholes, some of which are several hundred meters deep. Groundwater formed in the alluvial deposits of the Danube lowlands and the terraces of the larger rivers is also widely used. The least groundwater is used in areas where the water supply is provided by large dams, as well as in areas with sporadic distribution of groundwater in fractured reservoirs. On average for the country, about 17% of the available groundwater resources are used for drinking-household, industrial water supply, and agricultural production, and 2% for personal needs of the population (wells in yards). The amount of exploited water quantities in a territorial aspect depends, both on the water capacity of the exposed rocks, and on the population and economic condition of the respective region. According to the data of the Basin Directorates it is established that groundwater with the highest degree of usability accumulates in underground water bodies built of unrelated Quaternary and Neogene materials with relatively shallower lying pore waters (in the Danube lowlands - 39.3%, in graben-like depressions - 35.3% and alluvial deposits of larger rivers - 27.9%). More settlements, industrial enterprises and agriculture are developed in these areas.

Available groundwater resources differ from theoretically determined ones, in some cases because "pull out" resources from rivers are not taken into account in the overall water balance. Fracture waters are used the least (6-7%), mainly due to the fact that their exploitation can be carried out by capturing springs with low flow rates and due to the fact that they fall into sparsely populated, mountainous areas.

The territories of groundwater bodies in the inter river massifs of Northern Bulgaria are also less populated. By capturing springs with larger but highly variable flow rates, water is provided to settlements in the distribution zone of groundwater bodies associated with typical karst basins. The utilization rate of the available resources is about 12.6%.

Water bodies associated with artesian aquifers have been discovered in Northern and especially in Northeastern Bulgaria, where they are the only source of water for the population. The utilization rate of available groundwater resources is about 18%.

According to NIMH data, in 2022 significant variations of the water levels in the wells were found compared to the corresponding monthly norms and a very pronounced downward trend, registered in 45 observation points or about 73% of the observed cases.

The lowest water levels were recorded in the second half of 2022, most often in August (about 20%) and November (about 27%). Exceeding level deviations from the respective monthly norms (up to 68%) were found in the following groundwater basins: in places on the terraces of the Danube rivers (Karaboaz lowland), Skut and Fakiyska rivers, in parts of the Dupnishka and Kazanlak kettles. Deviations of average monthly water levels close to the norms were observed in the Sofia and Karlovska valleys, as well as in parts of the Upper Thracian lowland and the Malm-Valaginian aquifer complex (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Examples of deviations in average monthly flowrates of springs for 2022

CHALLENGES AND PROBLEMS IN THE USE AND PROTECTION OF GROUNDWATER

The main factors affecting the quantitative state of groundwater are climatic features and the intensity of groundwater extraction. The decrease of recharge from rainwater is related to the reduction of groundwater resources. On the other hand, the increase in average temperatures is related to the increase in water needs. This, in turn, affects the water quality.

According to data from the European Environment Agency, within the borders of the European Union, 65% of water for drinking purposes and 25% for agricultural needs are provided by groundwater. Data from second river basin management plans (2016) EU-27 show that 9% of groundwater bodies are in poor quantitative status. The main types of pressure are related to pollution and irrational use. Although the EU's environmental policy is showing results in the regulation of groundwater resources, the implementation of the regulations should be further accelerated. It is necessary to expand the monitoring observations in the spans of the water bodies, because often there are not enough points on large areas.

Bulgarian legislation fully follows the European framework in the field of water. The work of the Basin Directorates is related to the assessment of groundwater resources and the issuing of permits for water extraction by companies and individuals. Observed problems in previous years are related to the suspension of the construction of new wells due to lack of resources in certain water bodies (Pore waters in Neogene - Quaternary - Sofia Valley, BG1G00000NQ030). The reasons for this are the lack of a separate water body for the alluvial deposits in the Iskar river terrace, as well as the methodologically wrong approach of not taking into account the resources pull out from the rivers when preparing the general assessments. This is also valid for other parts of Bulgaria, and it is most striking for the water bodies bordering the Danube River. Establishing the relationship between surface water and groundwater is key to water management, which calls for more in-depth future research and the adoption of practical methods for resource assessment.

CONCLUSION

Groundwater is an important source of water supply, which is the only alternative in remote areas. The study and systematization of groundwater resources is related to the knowledge of the geological environment and the conditions of recharge and drainage of aquifers.

Bulgaria follows the water framework directive of the European Union, the aim of which is to preserve groundwater in good quantitative and qualitative condition. According to the Second River Basin Management Plans (2016-2021), natural groundwater resources amount to 193 m³/s. They are unevenly distributed across the country. The most groundwater accumulates in the Danube lowlands, artesian and alluvial aquifers.

The lowering of the levels in the shallow aquifers and the reduction of the flow rates of the springs present the impact of climate changes on the groundwater.

It is necessary to develop new approaches related to the use of modern information technologies, the expansion and digitization of the monitoring of groundwater. It is necessary collecting of data at a higher frequency and in a denser grids. The preparation of hydrogeological models for each specific water body will allow more accurate calculations of water quantities and a forecast of future impacts on the quantitative status.

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